

RADON AND ITS DETECTION: A REVIEW OF STUDY DONE SO FAR

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Abstract:

Radon is a chemical element with symbol Rn and its atomic no.86, it is colorless, odorless, tasteless radioactive gas and produced from the radioactive decay of the Uranium mainly which is found on in the rocks, soil and water. Rn is a most stable isotope of radon, which is found in atmosphere. It escapes from ground surface into air and construction material like sand, cement, bricks, gravel and tiles also. The radon exhalation rate is the number of radon atoms released per unit surface area per unit time from material like soil which is found over the ground water and Non-groundwater location. Radiation of a radon from a natural source is a one cause of environmental diseases. When long exposure to radon or excess concentration inhalation of radon leads to a lung cancer, next to smoking and sometimes radon poisoning. So, there is a need to estimate indoor and outdoor radon concentration of construction materials. In this article we outline the radon concentration and radon exhalation rate in soil samples, commonly used building construction material like cement, sand, bricks, granite material and indoor radon concentration review including methods to detect the radon concentration and exhalation rate in a selected sample or area.

Keywords: Radon, soil sample, Exhalation rate, Exposure.

1.1.Introduction:

Building materials are the second major source of indoor radon after soil. The contribution of building materials towards indoor radon depends upon the radium content and exhalation rates and can be used as a primary index for radon levels in the buildings. Radon is a radioactive hazardous and ubiquitous gas. It has been recognized to be one of the major contributors to natural radiation even causing lung cancer if present at enhanced levels. Radon is an atomic number 86 chemical element with the symbol Rn. A radioactive noble gas is colorless, odorless, and tasteless. It occurs naturally in minute amounts as an intermediary stage in the typical radioactive decay chains that slowly decay thorium and uranium into different short-lived radioactive elements and lead. Radon is the direct decay product of radium. Its most stable isotope, ^{222}Rn , has a 3.8-day half-life, making it one of the rarest elements. Because thorium and uranium are two of the most prevalent radioactive elements on Earth, and because radon has three isotopes with half-lives of several billion years, it will be present on Earth for a long time despite its short half-life. Radon decay yields several additional short-lived nuclides known as "radon daughters," which eventually end up as stable lead isotopes.

1.2.Radon Facts:

Radon is a radioactive gas that forms naturally when uranium, thorium, or radium, which are radioactive metals break down in rocks, soil and groundwater. People can be exposed to radon primarily from breathing radon in air that comes through cracks and gaps in buildings and homes. Radon gas is a ubiquitous element found in rock and soil. The burning of coal and other fossil fuels also release radon. When radon escapes from soil or is discharged from emission stacks to the outdoor air, it is diluted to levels that are normally, but not always, lower than indoor air.

1.3.Applications of Radon: -

Radon was sometimes used in hospitals to treat cancer and was produced as needed and delivered in sealed gold needles. Radon is used in hydrologic research, because of its rapid loss to air. It is also used in geologic research and to track air masses.

1.4.Radon in Environment :-

Radon can be found in some spring water and hot springs. There is anyway a detectable amount of radon in the atmosphere. Radon collects over samples of radium 226 at the rate of around 0.001 cm³/day per g of radium. Radon is a radioactive compound, which rarely occurs naturally in the environment. Most of the radon compounds found in the environment derive from human activities. Radon enters the environment through the soil, through uranium and phosphate mines, and through coal combustion. Some of the radon that is located in the soil will move to the surface and enter the air through vaporization. In the air, radon compounds will attach to dust and other particles. Radon can also move downwards in the soil and enter the groundwater. However, most of the radon will remain in the soil. Radon has a radioactive half-life of about four days; this means that one-half of a given amount of radon will decay to other compounds, usually less harmful compounds, every four days.

1.5.Health Effects of Radon:-

Radon occurs in the environment mainly in the gaseous phase. Consequently, people are mainly exposed to radon through breathing air. Background levels of radon in outside air are generally quite low, but in indoor locations radon levels in air may be higher. In homes, schools and buildings radon levels are increased because radon enters the buildings through cracks in the foundations and basements. Some of the deep wells that supply us with drinking water may also contain radon. As a result a number of people may be exposed to radon through drinking water, as well as through breathing air. Radon levels in groundwater are fairly high, but usually radon is quickly released into air as soon as the groundwater enters surface waters. Exposure to high levels of radon through breathing air is known to cause lung diseases. When long-term exposure occurs radon increases the chances of developing lung cancer. Radon can only cause cancer after several years of exposure. Radon may be radioactive, but it gives off little actual gamma radiation. As a result, harmful effects from exposure to radon radiation without actual contact with radon compounds are not likely to occur. It is not known whether radon can cause health effects in other organs besides the lungs. The effects of radon, which is found in food or drinking water, are unknown.

1.6.Discussion about radon:-

There is no debate about radon being a lung carcinogen in humans. All major national and international organizations that have examined the health risks of radon agree that it is a lung carcinogen. The scientific community continues to conduct research to refine our understanding of the precise number of deaths attributable to radon.

2.0. Radon Testing

The amount of radon emanating from the earth and concentrating inside homes varies considerably by region and locality. In 1988, EPA and the Office of the Surgeon General jointly recommended that all U.S. homes below the third floor be tested for radon. The National Academy of Sciences BEIR VI Report has estimated that radon causes about 15,000 to 22,000 lung cancer deaths annually based on their two-preferred models. Major scientific organizations continue to believe that approximately 12% of lung cancers annually in the United States are attributable to radon.

- || Currently, the only way to determine indoor radon concentration is by measuring it.
- || Radon only needs to be measured in inhabited areas of homes.
- || Measurement is the key to identifying the problem.
- || “Do-it-yourself” radon detection kits are available in most hardware stores.
- || Radon testing can also be done through a radon detection and remediation company.

2.1. Radon testing is required for all government buildings:

Radon is released into ambient air from soil and stones due to ubiquitous uranium and radium in them, thus increasing the airborne radon concentration. The radioactivity in soils is related to radioactivity in the rocks from which the soil is formed. Recent studies of people exposed to radon have confirmed that radon in homes represents a serious health hazard. The main health risk associated with long-term, elevated exposure to radon is an increased risk of developing lung cancer, which depends on the radon concentration and the length of exposure.

2.2. Radon Exhalation Rate:-

According to one study, the radon exhalation rate was 2 mBqm² h⁻¹ (Al- Shawawra location), with a total average value of 52.2 mBqm² h⁻¹. The mass exhalation rate was found to range between 0.26 and 7.84 mBqkg⁻¹ h⁻¹, with an average value of 1.97 mBqkg⁻¹ h⁻¹. All radium content readings in all samples tested were determined to be much lower than the worldwide threshold of 30 Bqkg⁻¹. Radon is a naturally occurring radioactive element that is created by the radioactive decay of radium isotopes, which are the decay products of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ²³⁵U. As a result, the quantity of radon generated in the soil is determined by the amounts of uranium and thorium in the soil types. Radon gas (²²²Rn) penetration from the earth has been recognized as one of the primary factors affecting indoor radon levels in many structures. According to one study, 60% of indoor radon originates from the ground and the soil around buildings. A large-scale indoor radon measurement has yet to be performed. However, a database based on regional geological surveys has been constructed in a number of locations.

There is a wealth of radiological data accessible, including uranium, thorium, and soil texture distribution. The release of radon from a substance to the atmosphere is referred to as exhalation. Radon molecules may escape from soil grains by diffusion or rebound into soil pores, a process known as emanation.

2.3. Source of radon:-

Radon is created naturally by the radioactive decay of uranium, which is present in all rocks and soils. Water may also contain radon. Radon escapes from the earth and into the atmosphere, where it decays and emits more radioactive particles. Radon gas penetration from the earth into buildings is the primary cause of indoor radon. Radon gas is produced by rocks and dirt. Radon may enter the house via building materials, water supplies, and natural gas. Basements provide greater space for soil gas penetration than slab-on-grade foundations. Radon is a naturally occurring radioactive gas that has the potential to cause lung cancer. Radon gas is colorless, odorless, and inactive. Radon is naturally present in tiny concentrations in the atmosphere. Radon dissipates quickly outside and is typically not a health concern.

2.4. Radon Migration process, radon exhalation rate and national & international status:-

It is well known that radon atom is generated from the decay of radium atom inside the solid grain in the soil. A fraction of radon atoms leaves those solid grains to the soil pores. This fraction of radon atoms, which escaped from solid grains into the pore space, is called emanation coefficient. To understand the emanation coefficient process of radon into pore space, we should follow the explanation of emanation process. When radium atom decays to radon atom, alpha particle is emitted immediately. Each of them will take a part of energy inversely proportional with their masses i.e. alpha particle will take 104 to 105 times greater than radon atom (86–103 keV). Each of alpha particle and radon atom will move in opposite direction due to momentum conservation. Radon atom will move in its direction until its energy transferred to the host materials. It can travel 20–70 nm in common minerals, 100 nm in water, and 63 μ m in air, this distance called recoiling radon range. Radon range varied according to the different composition of the medium. When radon gas was generated in solid grain, it had three possibilities, it may travel and remain embedded in the same grain, it may travel across a pore space and become embedded in the adjacent grain, or released into the pore space and stopped. If there was a liquid in the pore space, the radon atoms may stop there which will increase the emanation coefficient. The implanted radon atom in the adjacent grain may be escaped to the pore space again, thus enable to escape out by diffusion while its path was still

molten.

Radium concentration in the investigating materials should be measured using γ -spectroscopy. Then, radon emanation coefficient can be calculated by dividing radon activity concentration (Bq) in that space by the radium activity concentration (Bq) in those materials. Therefore all methods used to measure radon isotopes equilibrium concentrations in closed space can be used to measure radon emanation coefficient by combining with a method to measure radium content in the investigating materials. Measurement of gamma rays emitted from nuclides ^{226}Ra was performed by measuring gamma rays of energy 352 keV for ^{214}Pb , 609 keV for ^{214}Bi after the radioactive equilibrium was achieved between them and its parent, ^{226}Ra . The sample materials are first dried at 105°C for at least 24 hours (standard conditions). Then the samples are put in appropriated container and are completely sealed to avoid the air to enter it or escape from it. Finally, this sealed container was kept for one month to achieve the secular equilibrium and then ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi isotopes were measured with a Gamma rays monitor (High Purity Germanium Detector, HPGe).

This method was approved by many researches. It is understood that the radon emanation coefficient increases with increase of temperature. This may arise from the adsorption process of gases on solid grain will decrease i.e. the increase in temperature markedly decreases the amount of adsorbed gas.²⁸⁾ Iskandar³²⁾ estimated a formula to calculate the emanation coefficient at different temperature, $\epsilon_c = \epsilon + 0.21 (T_c - T)$ (10) Where, ϵ , the measured emanation coefficient (%), T is soil temperature at the time of sampling, ϵ_c is the calculated radon emanation coefficient (%) at a particular temperature (T_c).

Residential radon exposure alone is projected to have caused 84,000 lung cancer deaths globally in 2019; in certain countries, it is one of the top causes of lung cancer. The naturally occurring radioactive gas is a major cause of lung cancer in persons who have never smoked. It may accumulate in structures (homes, schools, and workplaces) and in water, although its health risk can be mitigated. There are well-tested, long-lasting, and cost-effective ways for radon prevention in new homes as well as measuring and reducing it in existing homes. More countries have recognized the opportunity to prevent radon exposure and have been developing policies, regulations, and national action plans to respond to this indoor air pollutant, including through education for building professionals and the provision of financial assistance to remove it from existing buildings. However, just 12% of examined nations have offered radon education for construction professionals, 15% have provided financial assistance to repair old structures, and no country has incorporated mandated radon readings in property transactions. In the nearly 16 years since the WHO first surveyed countries as part of the WHO

International Radon Project, awareness and action on radon have grown, but much work remains to be done for most countries to achieve radon concentrations at or below the WHO recommended reference level of 100 Bq/m³ if possible, or at least not to exceed the international recommended 300 Bq/m³. The World Health Organization advises that nations adopt gas reference limits of 100 Bq/m³ (Becquerel per cubic metre). If this level cannot be met under the current country-specific circumstances, WHO advises that the reference level not exceed 300 Bq/m³.

3.0. Literature Review on the Radon measurement:

Author's Name	Locations	Radon Exhalation Rate
Soil Sample: Joga Singh et al. (2009)	Upper Siwaliks of Kala Amb, Nahan and Morni Hills, Northern India	Radon in soil varies from 28.3 ± 0.5 to 81.0 ± 1.7 Bqkg ⁻¹ , 61.2 ± 1.3 to 140.3 ± 2.6 Bqkg ⁻¹ and 363.4 ± 4.9 to 1002.2 ± 11.2 Bqkg ⁻¹ respectively.
Dhawal et al. (2013)	Kokan, Maharashtra	Radon in soil samples varied from 44.97 ± 1.22 Bqkg ⁻¹ , 59.70 ± 2.17 Bqkg ⁻¹ and 217.51 ± 8.75 Bqkg ⁻¹ respectively.
Mir et al. (2014)	Ganderbal district of Kashmir	Radon varies from 5.05 mBqkg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ to 21.89 mBqkg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ and 6.43 to 18.89 Bqkg ⁻¹ respectively.
Chauhan et al. (2014)	Kurukshetr and Yamunanagar.	Radon surface exhalation rate in soil samples is 28.2 - 91.2 mBqkg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ and 48 - 191 mBqm ⁻² h ⁻¹ respectively
R. Jakhu et al. (2018)	Jaipur and Ajmer district of Rajasthan	Radio nucleotide concentration vary from 5.20 to 26.29 mBq ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ and activity concentration of ²²⁶ Ra, ²³² Th and ⁴⁰ K ranges from 34 Bqkg ⁻¹ - 73 Bqkg ⁻¹ with mean value of 55 Bqkg ⁻¹ , 30 Bqkg ⁻¹ - 145 Bqkg ⁻¹ with mean value of 69 Bqkg ⁻¹ and 622 Bqkg ⁻¹ - 1082 Bqkg ⁻¹ with mean value of 874 Bqkg ⁻¹ .

Kaur et al. (2018)	Siwalik Himalayas	The radon mass exhalation rate varies from 7 to 48 $\text{mBq}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ and thoron surface exhalation rate varies from 123 to 2606 $\text{Bqm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$
Building Material & Soil Sample: Kant et al.(2001)	Northern India from Ballabgarh, Hariyana.	Radon varied from Coal samples - 433 ± 28 to $2086 \pm 28 \text{Bq.m}^{-3}$ and 748 ± 28 , Fly ash samples - $1417 \pm 111 \text{Bq.m}^{-3}$, Cement samples - 158 to 1810Bq.m^{-3} .
Gaur Bala et.al. (2001)	Unna and Hamirpur district, Himachal Pradesh.	Radon from building material varies from $39.1 \text{mBqkg}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ to $91.2 \text{mBqkg}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ with mean value $59.7 \text{mBqkg}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ and $40.72 \text{mBqkg}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$, Sandstone to $81.40 \text{mBqkg}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ for granite respectively.
Chauhan and Chakravarti (2002)	North India	Radon varied from 433 ± 28 to $2086 \pm 36 \text{Bq.m}^{-3}$ using SSNTDs. Thermal power plants varied from 558 ± 40 to $682 \pm 60 \text{Bq.m}^{-3}$
Gupta and Chauhan (2011)	North-Eastern Haryana state of India	Radioactivity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K were varied from 18 ± 1.5 to $156 \pm 6 \text{Bqkg}^{-1}$, 23 ± 1 to $300 \pm 5 \text{Bqkg}^{-1}$ and 32 ± 0.5 to $1705 \pm 14 \text{Bqkg}^{-1}$ respectively
Building material: Walley et al (2001) (building material)	Egypt and foreign	It was varied from 5.46 ± 0.16 to $150.52 \pm 4.52 \text{Bq.kg}^{-1}$ for marble samples and from 229.52 ± 6.89 to $92.16 \pm 2.76 \text{Bq.kg}^{-1}$ for granite
Kovler et al (2002) (Building material)	Industrial Biproduct	Radioactivity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K were 35, 72, and 585Bq.kg^{-1} , respectively
A M El-Arabi et al (2006)	Nile valley	Radon concentration varied from 36.1 ± 2 to 96.4 ± 6 , 17.8 ± 3 to 73.6 ± 4 and 18.0 ± 2 to $188.1 \pm 15 \text{Bq.m}^{-3}$
Sonkawade et. al.(2008)	Kolhapur District, India	Radon Exhalation varied between 333 ± 9.9 to $506 \pm 13.3 \text{Bqm}^{-3}$ and 3.7 ± 0.1 to $5.6 \pm 0.2 \text{Bqkg}^{-1}$ while in various cementations finishing materials it was found to be 378 ± 19.7 to $550 \pm 9.8 \text{Bqm}^{-3}$ and 4.2 ± 0.2 to $6.1 \pm 0.1 \text{Bqkg}^{-1}$ respectively

Y. Raghu and Ravishankar R (2015)	Pachal of Tiruvannamalai District, Tamilnadu.	The minimum concentration of ^{226}Ra is 7.47Bq/kg measured in sand while the highest value is 31.26Bqkg^{-1} measured in cement . The lowest value for ^{232}Th is 27.09Bqkg^{-1} was recorded in sand sample and the highest value is 77.8Bqkg^{-1} obtained in clay sample .
Water: Binesh et. al. (2012) (Water)	Mashhad Iran	Radon ranges from 0.064 Bq l^{-1} to 46.088 Bq l^{-1} with a mean value of 16.24 Bq l^{-1} .
Kumar et al. (2016) (Water)	Amritsar city, Punjab.	Radon varies from $0.53 \pm 0.11\text{ Bq l}^{-1}$ to $11.20 \pm 1.40\text{ Bq l}^{-1}$. The annual effective dose varies from 1.45 to $30.57\text{ }\mu\text{Svy}^{-1}$.
Indoor: Quirino et al (2007)	State of Zacatecas	The average, minimum and maximum concentrations are 67 , 26 and 511Bq.m^{-3} , respectively

The average radioactivity content of the three primordial radionuclides in soil samples for India and the rest of the world have been provided by the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation Sources (UNSCEAR-2000). The average value for ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in the world is 33 , 45 , and 420 Bqkg^{-1} , respectively, while the average value for ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in India is 29 , 64 , and 400 Bqkg^{-1} , respectively. In comparison to the global average of 35Bq.kg^{-1} , Indian soil has a ^{238}U concentration of 29Bq.kg^{-1} . According to the literature research, the mean values for the activity of primordial radionuclides like ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in Indian soils are respectively 29 , 64 , and 400 Bq/kg . These ranges are 7 to 81 , 14 to 160 , and 38 to 880 Bq/kg , respectively. In cement, radionuclides including ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K have activity concentrations that range from 16 to 377 , 2 to 385 , and detectors were fixed to the lower side of cork lids, which are then gently pressed against the polyethylene sheets on the glass bottles (acting as emanation chambers) to ensure that the equilibrium is not disturbed or is disturbed as little as possible, if at all. The chambers were sealed with adhesive tape after tightly closing the cork lids to reduce leakage, and they were left that way for three months so that the detectors could record alpha particles produced by the decay of radon (Mehra et al., 2006).

2.4. Various methods for measurement of Radon:-

An extensive literature review on radon exhalation in underground uranium mines from various sources such as uranium ore, backfill tailings and mine water has been carried out. The influence of different important factors, viz. ore grade, porosity, grain size and moisture content on radon exhalation has been discussed in depth. Few techniques are as mentioned below,

a) By measuring the radon concentration at two locations,

Thompkins and Rajhans (1967) described a method for the estimation of the radon exhalation rate in underground uranium mines. In this method, uncontaminated air is supplied at different velocities through a raise of uniform cross-section and 30 to 50 m long. Filtered air samples are collected in Lucas flasks at two locations separated by a known distance at predetermined time intervals. Radon exhalation rate 'J' ($\text{Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) is calculated using the following relation:

$$J = \frac{(C_2 - C_1)Q}{PL}$$

where C_1 is the initial radon concentration in one location, ($\text{Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$),

C_2 is the final radon concentration in another location ($\text{Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$),

Q is the airflow rate ($\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), P is the perimeter of the stope (m) and L is the length of the stope (m).

However, this method is not suitable where the stopes are inter connected and large uncertainties in the results may be observed due to various mining operation conditions, contamination of intake air and air leakage.

Charcoal canister method

Lawrence, Akber, Bollhofer, and Martin (2009) used charcoal canisters for measuring the radon exhalation rate. These canisters are filled with 25 g of activated charcoal and then heated in an oven for 24 h prior to desorption of any previously adsorbed ^{222}Rn . After removal from the oven, the canisters are sealed and taken to the sampling location where they are unsealed, upturned and pressed firmly into the ground to about 1 cm depth to ensure a good seal between the edge of the canister and the ground. The canisters are again sealed after collecting the sample for four to five days and then sent to the laboratory. The activity of ^{222}Rn adsorbed on the charcoal is determined by counting the gamma particles emitted from ^{214}Pb .

and ^{214}Bi using a gamma spectrometer with a NaI(Tl) crystal housed in a sealed castle. The ^{222}Rn exhalation rate is determined using the following equation,

$$J = \frac{Rt_c \lambda^2 \exp(\lambda t_d)}{\varepsilon a [1 - \exp(-\lambda t_c)] [1 - \exp(-\lambda t_d)]}$$

where J is the radon exhalation rate ($\text{Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), R is the net count rate after background subtraction during the counting period " t_c " (counts s^{-1}), t_c is the counting period (s), λ is the decay constant of radon (s^{-1}), t_d is the delay period from the end of exposure to the beginning of the counting interval (s), ε is the counting efficiency of the system (counts $\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Bq}^{-1}$), a is the area of the canister (m^2) and t_e is the period of exposure of the charcoal in the canister (s). A lower detection limit of $1.11 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ for a four-day exposure period by using charcoal canister has been reported by Countess.

The flow method

Some researchers measured the average radon exhalation over a large area of the tailings by circulating air under a collector through a charcoal bed (Freeman, 1981). Pacific Northwest Laboratory (PNL) developed a re-circulating, pressure balanced, flow-through radon exhalation measuring system that uses a $76 \times 122 \times 5 \text{ cm}$ (9300 cm^2 surface area) aluminium tent to cover the area to be measured. The system utilizes a diaphragm vacuum pump to draw air through a diorite column to remove water vapour and through a filter to remove particulates. The air is then passed through an activated carbon trap to remove radon. The carbon trap consists of a 4.8 cm diameter convoluted tube filled with 400 g of 8–12 mesh size activated carbon. This trap can absorb 99.9% of the radon in the air that is circulating through the trap at a rate of 2 litres per minute at temperature of 44°C . The system is sealed to tailings by pushing the lip of the tent into the tailings. After about four hours of sampling, the ^{222}Rn activity concentration is determined by counting the gamma particles emitted from ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi using an intrinsic germanium gamma-ray spectrometer and the radon exhalation is then determined from the radon concentration value.

Accumulation method

In the accumulation method, the quantitative estimation of the radon exhalation rate from the materials is made by measuring the build-up of radon activity concentration in the accumulation chamber. Thompkins and Cheng (1969) have used the accumulation method for measuring the in situ radon exhalation rate from the ore wall in an underground uranium mine. In this method, they prepared different sampling points by cutting a flat surface of 1 m × 1 m × 12 cm deep on the fore wall. A steel frame was mounted on the flat area of the wall and cemented in that position. The frame was connected to the steel chamber, which was provided with several valves. The chamber served for the accumulation of radon exhaled from the ore. The chamber was initially flushed with compressed air to remove the radon gas and the valves were then closed. Air samples were collected from the chamber at intervals of several hours up to a maximum of 50 hours for the determination of radon exhalation rate. However, this method is very complex, expensive and time consuming when arranging the experimental setup. Raghavayya and Khan (1973) used a drum of about 25 l capacity and 600 cm² cross-sectional area opened at one end for determination of radon exhalation rate from the mill tailings used as backfill in underground uranium mines. A tube provided with stopcock was fitted onto the closed end of the drum through a rubber cork. The drum was partially buried in the backfilled tailings up to a depth of approximately 20 cm, so that the radon gas exhalating through the surface of backfill material filled into the enclosed volume without leakage. An initial air sample was drawn with a scintillation flask soon after burying the drum and the second air sample was drawn after some hours in order to determine the radon concentration in each sampling. The radon exhalation rate was then deduced from initial and second radon concentration values. However, this technique also has some limitations like the occurrence of back diffusion and leakage of air due to a longer experiment period giving rise to uncertainty in the results. Since the height of the drum is large, radon may not mix uniformly inside the drum and hence it may require employing a small fan inside the drum for proper mixing. In addition, the larger size of the drum is not convenient from the point of view of portability, especially for large-scale field study inside the mine. The radon exhalation from uranium mill tailings using a method similar to that used by They used a small cylindrical steel chamber of 2l capacity for the accumulation of exhaled radon for about 30–60 min. The open end of the chamber was placed tightly over the radon-exhaling surface and the closed end was provided with a Swagelok.

E) AQTEK SMART RnDuo Detector.

Measurement of exhalation rate of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn :

The active device AQTEK SMART RnDuo is used to assess radon content and exhalation rate in soil and building materials in current work. The SMART RnDuo is a commercially available portable instrument that detects ^{222}Rn , ^{220}Rn , and alpha rays in the air, ground, and water. The basic principle of the SMART RnDuo instrument is to detect alpha particles using ZnS: Ag scintillation. The acquisition policy and measurement processes are described in further detail elsewhere (Gaware *et al.* 2011). Study materials samples (~ 1000 g) such as rock, sand, various types of cement are obtained from local markets, construction sites, and soil samples has been collected over GW and Non-GW zones for the mass exhalation rate of ^{222}Rn , ^{220}Rn and concentration. A mortar and pestle or a vibrating ball machine are used to grind the sample into a fine powder. To test radon, a fine powder of an object is placed in the exhalation chamber. The Smart RnDuo is coupled to a ~700gm sample capacity closed accumulation.

^{222}Rn Exhalation Rate is calculated by using following formula:

$$J_m = \frac{BV}{M}$$

^{220}Rn Exhalation Rate is calculated by using following formula:

$$J_s = \frac{C_d}{A}$$

F) RRC passive radiometer:

The RRC passive radiometer (Uvarov and Kulakov, 1995), which was specifically created to avoid radon, dust, and moisture penetration into the detector chamber, is used to quantify the amount of radon in soil. The radiometer consists of a plastic layer sandwiched between an aluminum cylindrical chamber with an inner diameter of 3.2 cm and a volume of 17 cm³ and a cover. The chamber wall has twelve 6 mm-diameter holes for radon ingress that are protected by a 35 m-thick polyethylene covering. The detector is mounted to a central holder in a drum-style support. A 13 mm thick layer of aluminized Mylar absorber lines the inside of the holder, reducing the energy of α -particles and shielding the cellulose nitrate detector (CND) from errant electrostatic charges. Diffusion allows radon to enter the radiometer through a polyethylene layer. Decomposition byproducts plate out on the radiometer's inside surface. Only the detection of α -particles released by radon products that are plated out on the Al-Mylar is possible

with the CND in use (Russian-made, K-8 type, thickness of 13 m, density 1.49 0.01 g/cm³). The radiometer makes it very easy to assess the level of radon in moist soil. When chemically etching CND for 100 minutes at 50 °C in 5N NaOH solution, its sensitivity is 0.7 0.2 (track/cm²)/(kBqhm⁻³). The CN detector's background is thus 70 20 tracks/cm². A spark counter is used to read out the detectors. The depth of the soil determines the radon concentration there, and it rises with depth (Jonsson, 1995).

G) Cellulose Nitrate Plastic Track Detector

The alpha particles released by radon, thoron, and their offspring have been detected using the cellulose nitrate (CN) plastic detector, commercially known as LR-115 Type-II with chemical composition C₆H₈O₉N₂. It is a film with a red layer of nitrate that is between 11.5 and 12 microns thick and is deposited over a clear polyester foundation that is 100 microns thick (and etchable). The primary alpha particle energy range detected by the LR-115 Type II plastic track detector is 1.7 to 4.8 MeV. (1981; Abu-Jarad et al., 1980; Jonsson). Because their alpha energies (6.0 and 7.68 MeV from ²¹⁸Po and ²¹⁴Po, respectively) are higher than the upper threshold energy of the LR-115 Type II plastic track detector, any more alpha particles released by radon daughters won't be detected on its surface. Humidity, low temperature, moderate heating, and light have little effect on the benefits of LR-115 Type II detectors (Durrani and Ili, 1997). Electrons and electromagnetic radiation (such as gamma, X, ultraviolet, and infrared rays) have no impact on LR-115 films.

H) Alpha guard equipment and Gamma Tracer was applied for gamma dose rate measurements:

The measuring setup included an Alpha Guard PQ 2000 PRO (AG) radon monitor, a soil-gas probe, and an Alpha-Pump (AP) to determine the amount of radon in soil gas, or CR_n (Bqm³) (Genitron, Germany). A flow of 0.3 dm³ min⁻¹ of soil gas was pumped through the AG ionization chamber. Over roughly 20 minutes, the transient radon (²²²Rn) concentrations were measured at one-minute intervals. Following an early period of rise, the concentration stabilized. The radon concentration in soil gas was determined to be the mean of the most recent stabilized values. The contribution of thoron (²²⁰Rn, half-life 55 s) was minimal at this low flow rate (Zuni'c et al., 2006).

D) Closed Can Technique:

This method is used to calculate the rate at which radon is exhaled from soil samples. 40 soil samples were taken, and they were placed in tidy, dry plastic bags. To obtain the natural soil, the dirt was extracted from an auger hole that was dug around 0.75 meters below the surface. Samples are cleaned of stones and organic matter before being ground into a fine powder in a mortar and pestle. The material is finely filtered using a scientific sieve with a mesh size of 150 μ m. The samples were then dried for 24 hours at 110 °C in an oven to remove any remaining moisture. A glass bottle with a volume of around 1 L served as the emission chamber. To achieve equilibrium between the radium-radon members of the decay series, the fine powder (0.25 kg) of samples was deposited at the bottom of the glass bottles and covered with thin polyethylene sheets for 1 month. After a month, 1.5 cm \times 1.5 cm LR-115 type II plastic track detectors were fixed to the lower side of cork lids, which are then gently pressed against the polyethylene sheets on the glass bottles (acting as emanation chambers) to ensure that the equilibrium is not disturbed or is disturbed as little as possible, if at all. The chambers were sealed with adhesive tape after tightly closing the cork lids to reduce leakage, and they were left that way for three months so that the detectors could record alpha particles produced by the decay of radon (Mehra et al., 2006).

Table 1 : Values of concentration and exhalation rate of Radon concentration in different countries as compared with other study.

Country	Area Exhalation (Bqm-2h-1)	Mass Exhalation (mBqKg-2h-1)	References
India	0.76	2.3	B. P. Singh, B Pandit, V N Bhardwaj, Paramjit Singh, Rajesh Kumar , “A Study of radium and radon exhalation rate in some solid samples using solid state nuclear track detectors”, Indian Journal of Pure & Applied Physics , 48, pp. 493-495, 2010
Saudi Arabi a	8.4	251	S. M. Farid , “Indoor Radon in dwellings of Jeddah city, Saudi Arabia and its Correlations with the radium and radon exhalation rates from soil,” Indoor and Built Environment , DOI: 10.1177/1420326X14536749, 2014.

Egypt	-	-	K. A. Korany, A. E. Shata, S. F. Hassam, M. S. E. Nagdy, “Depth and seasonal Variations for the soil Radon -Gas Concentration Levels at Wadi Naseib Area, Southwestern Sinai, Egypt,” J. Phys. Chem. Biophys, 3, pp. 123, 2013. doi:10.4172/2161-0398.1000123
Kassala, Sudan	-	-	Abdelmoniem A. Elzain, A. K. Sam, O. M. Mukhtar and M. A. Abbasher “Measurements of Radon Gas Concentration in a soil at some Towns in Kassala State.” Gezira Journal of Engineering & Applied Sciences,4(1), pp.15-42,2009.
Rabak, Sudan	7.2	145	Abdelmoniem A. Elzain, Y. Sh. Mohammed, Kh. Sh. Mohammed, Sumaia S. M “Radium and Radon Exhalation Studies in Some Soil Samples from Singa and Rabak Towns, Sudan using CR-39,” International Journal of Science and Research, volume 3 Issue 11, November 2014, ISSN: 2319-7064
Singa, Sudan	17.6	354	Abdelmoniem A. Elzain, Y. Sh. Mohammed, Kh. Sh.

Conclusion:-

Knowledge of radon sources and quantitative assessment of radon from diverse sources are important for regulating radiation levels in underground uranium mines. This study describes radon exhalation sources and monitoring methodologies in uranium mines. Radon exhalation in underground uranium mines relies on ore grade, porosity, grain size, and moisture content. The radon exhalation rate in porous uranium-bearing rocks is less impacted by ore grade than

in non-porous rocks, according to the literature. Due to larger bulk porosity and surface area, tailings exhale more radon than ore. Porosity dominates radon gas exhalation from rock faces into mine holes. Flowing water through uranium-bearing rocks may also produce radon in mines. Flowing water increases radon concentration in mine air depending on turbulence and airflow rate. Measuring radon exhalation from diverse sources is vital for reducing radiation levels and protecting workers from radiation threats. Using different-sized accumulators, researchers detected radon exhalation in uranium mines. Smaller accumulators increase back diffusion, which affects radon exhalation. Large accumulators aren't portable, particularly for mine field research. In taller accumulators, radon may not mix uniformly, requiring a modest fan for optimum mixing and dispersion. For a longer radon build-up duration in the accumulation chamber, back diffusion may occur and the correction factor may be more important, which decreases exponentially with a shorter build-up period. To prevent back diffusion in the accumulator, pick the optimal accumulator size and radon build-up duration for radon exhalation measurements in underground uranium mines. High radon danger has also been recorded in coal, gold, copper, and manganese mines, thus radon exhalation should be measured in these mines to restrict radiation levels to safe levels.

Most settlements have typical uranium soil concentrations. Higher uranium concentrations in rocks of Tusham ring complex, Haryana, are attributable to high-heat granites (HHPG). The average radon mass exhalation rate is 59.7 mBq kg⁻¹ h⁻¹. The area's radium content ranges from 30.6 to 51.9 Bq kg⁻¹ with a mean of 41.6. Geological formation affects radon exhalation rate. Granite exhales more radon than marble and sandstone. All construction materials should be tested for radon exhalation and have a standard code. This reduces radon levels in new buildings, particularly in new locales. 12.6 to 169.0 mBq m⁻² h⁻¹ is the radon exhalation rate. Unfired clay bricks emit the most radon, whereas bleached limestone emits the least. Fired clay bricks emit less radon than unfired bricks and sand. Sand's radon level seems significant, and the amount used is considerable compared to cement. Sand contributes little to natural radiation exposure. The findings show normal to higher radon levels in stone and soil samples from north India's Aravali Hills. Granite diorite and granite samples have greater amounts than other white stones.

Three models computed indoor radon concentration from observed radon exhalation rate from various building materials. To verify these models' predictions, indoor radon concentration was measured in selected homes using a calibrated pin-hole dosimeter. Accumulator methods detected radon surface flux from selected floors. Scintillation monitors assess radon mass and surface exhalations. All three models predicted close-to-measured radon concentrations.

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